

The Role of Brand Personality in e-Marketing: A Computational Approach

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Abstract

Brand personality refers to the set of human characteristics or traits that can be associated with a brand (Aaker, 1997) and gives consumers something with which they can relate to which effectively increases brand awareness, popularity and brand loyalty. By establishing a brand personality, businesses can form emotional bonds with their consumers. Empirical research on brand-consumer relationships has shown that brand personality enables consumers to express their self, forming and strengthening the relationship between brands and consumers (e.g. Aaker, Fournier, and Brasel 2004). In the present study, in order to delineate and highlight the role and the impact of brand personality in e-marketing, dimensions of personality and parameters of emotional intelligence are being studied.

For the data collection, three self-report questionnaires were administered: Brand Personality Appeal [BPA], Eysenck Personality Questionnaire [EPQ] and Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire [TEIQue]. There were being created their electronic versions through Google Forms service and posted through the website “<http://www.cicos.gr/iccmi2017/rbpm>”. Then the collected data were selected for analysis, with relevant transformations in order to have a suitable form for the implementation of the respective machine learning algorithms included in the software package R.

The results of the present study show among others that emotions, personality dimensions can serve as outcome variables and can be prevalent in the marketing literature covering a wide range of topics, including evidence that emotions and personality traits of the consumers are generated by the use of specific products in specific mostly known brands.

Keywords: Brand Personality, Emotional Intelligence, Consumers, Social Networks, R, Computational Methods

1. INTRODUCTION

Realizing that brand personality plays an important role in the success of a brand, this study explores the impact of brand personality expression on the quality of brand relationship and WOM transmission in relation to the personality and emotional intelligence dimensions of the consumer. It is one of the first researches on this issue that applies to Greek populism. Also, in this study we look at the role of consumers in advertising, recognizability and psychological proximity to a particular brand as a case study, Apple.

1.1. Brand Personality Appeal (BPA)

The personality of a trademark consists of a combination of human features associated with a brand. Consumers use the personality of a brand name as a means of personal identification but also positioning on the product in question, with the result that it often appears as a personality identity with the personality of that trademark. Within a consumer society, a brand is no longer the subject of financial exchange, recognition, and consumers themselves. Consumers use the brand when their personality helps them identify, place, and recognize themselves. Such an adaptation of course also depends on the ability of the mark to make it attractive to consumers. For this reason, the brand personality must be discreet, attractive and recognizable to all consumers. These brand features determine its personality, the ability of a brand to reach consumers by combining the human characteristics associated with it. Many empirical researches on brand-consumer relationships has shown that brand personality allows consumers to express themselves by shaping and enhancing the relationship between brands and consumers. For this reason, consumers tend to build, develop and strengthen their relationship with the brand.

Figure 1 Conceptual Model

The Conceptual Model of Brand Personality Appeal Scale:

- H1: Brand relationship quality has a positive effect on WOM transmission.
- H2: Brand personality appeal has a positive effect on brand relationship quality.
- H3: Brand personality appeal has a positive effect on WOM transmission.
- H4: Attitudes toward advertising have a positive effect on brand personality appeal.
- H5: Attitudes toward advertising have a positive effect on brand relationship quality.
- H6: Attitudes toward public relations have a positive effect on brand personality appeal.
- H7: Attitudes toward public relations have a positive effect on brand relationship quality.

1.2. Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (EPQ)

The personality dimensions introduced by Eysenck are separate types of people, each of which involves a set of features traced back to their habits and their specific reactions. In particular, what is proposed is the detection of specific reactions of the individual, which will give evidence of his usual reactions and hence of his usual behavior. This will allow conclusions to be drawn for some key features of his personality. These attributes are considered as the factors that make up each of the three dimensions of personality (types). The relationship between the reactions and their regular appearance makes them reliable criteria for rendering certain characteristics to the personality of the person. That is, dimensions or types of personality are notions that include a group of related characteristics, which we deduce from the study of reactions and behavior of the individual. In detail, the three dimensions of the personality that are proposed have the following

Image 1

characteristics:

- **Extraversion-introversion**[Activity, Sociability, Assertiveness, Expressiveness, Ambition, Dogmatism, and Aggressiveness]: One who is defined as extrovert is social, loves gatherings, has many friends, and does not like reading and studying. Also, has a keen desire for emotion, does not lose opportunities, likes danger, reacts immediately and is generally impulsive.
- **Neurotism - Instability - Emotional Stability**[Inferiority, Unhappiness, Anxiety, Dependence, Hypochondria, Guilt, Obsessiveness]: Neurotism refers to the general emotional instability of the individual, to its emotional hyperactivity and to the tendency to develop neurotic symptoms under stress.
- **Psychoticism**[Risk-taking, Impulsivity, Irresponsibility, Manipulativeness, Sensation-seeking, Tough-mindedness, Practicality]: Further exploration of Eysenck's personality dimensions has led to the observation that there is one more personality variable that manifests in the population as a whole - that is, in healthy and divergent - in the form of reaction patterns and is indicative of the possible appearance of psychotic elements. This variable was the third personality dimension, called "Psychotism" (P) and also refers to subjective personality traits. This predisposition exists to varying degrees in all individuals, and only its very high value may be an indication of some form of psychosis. The result of these observations was the development of a measurement scale of the three dimensions of the personality (E, N, P) and a complementary dimension of the L, which measures the falsehood of the answers given by the person questioned during the questionnaire. The new scale, presented by the Eysenck couple in 1975, was named the Eysenck Personality Questionnaire (E.P.Q.).

1.3. Trait Emotional Intelligence (EI)

The Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire is a self-report questionnaire that has been developed to cover the trait EI sampling domain comprehensively. Questionnaire measures of EI have been proliferating over the past few years, and it is important to mention three advantages of the TEIQue over them to justify the focus of this research. First, the TEIQue is based on a psychological theory that integrates the construct into mainstream models of differential psychology. Second, the TEIQue provides comprehensive coverage of the 15 facets of the trait EI sampling domain. Several independent studies have demonstrated the ability of the TEIQue to predict criteria (outcomes) significantly better than other questionnaires. Third, the full TEIQue has excellent psychometric properties. Finally, the TEIQue has been used in numerous studies wherein the assessment of affective aspects of personality was required. These include research in the areas of neuroscience, relationship satisfaction, psychopathology, addictions, reaction time, general health, and behavioral genetics. The TEIQue provides an operationalization for the model of Petrides and colleagues that conceptualizes EI in terms of personality. The test encompasses 15 subscales organized under four factors: well-being, self-control, emotionality and sociability.

Image 2

- **Well being:** The Well-being factor comprises three different traits: Happiness, Optimism and Self-esteem. They measure how people judge their general level of life satisfaction.
- **Self control:** The Self-control factor describes how far people think they can control their impulses or are controlled by them. It comprises three different traits: Impulse Control, Stress Management and Emotional Regulation.
- **Emotionality:** The Emotionality factor comprises four different traits: Empathy, Emotion Perception, Emotion Expression and Relationships. Together they indicate how aware you may be of your own

emotions and feelings, as well as those of other people. Scores on these traits tend to reflect how highly you value this 'emotional literacy' and when and how you make use of it.

- **Sociability:** The Sociability factor describes how comfortable people feel in different social contexts, from parties and social gatherings to formal business meetings.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this paper were applied Machine Learning and Data Mining methods in order to evaluate and associate the Brand Personality Appeal (BPA) with Personality Dimensions (EPQ) and Emotional Intelligence (TEIQue) of social network consumers. The methodology, that was adopted, consists of three concrete phases. During the first phase electronic questionnaires were created and posted through the website <http://www.cicos.gr>. Subsequently, data were collected and preprocessed from the questionnaires. The data set for analysis was consisted of demographics elements of responders, such as the gender, the birth-place, the place of present residence, educational background of both the respondents and their parents, professional occupation of parents and also of subscales of the BPA, EPQ and TEIQue tests. During the third phase, the data set was analyzed based on Data Mining techniques and evaluate the results. More specifically, we utilized classification algorithms so as to manage to describe the hidden patterns underlying in the data. Decision trees are a powerful way in order to represent and facilitate statements analysis (psychological) principally, comprising successive decisions and variable results in a designated period.

2.1. Brand Name as a tool in Consumer Behavior

Developing a personality in a brand is to the benefit of the company. However, the challenges presented in this process are many but also complex. The goal for companies is to develop a way to meet their customers' needs better and to create long-lasting consumer-brand relationships. To accomplish this, it presupposes that the company needs to establish its own trademark a unique personality based on human characteristics. This creates a strong link between the brand and the consumer. These strong relationships may promote consumer engagement in that brand. Brand personality can even explain how consumer-brand relationships affect consumer behavior as the concept of personality is based on the idea that a consumer attraction appears and is enhanced by depicting a personality similar to the personality of the consumer.

There are three specific conditions where the brand works and relates to consumer behavior.

- The first treaty concerns the personality of the brand as a means to express the benefits of a trademark. It is easier for a brand to create a personality that implies the operational benefits of trying to get these benefits directly into the consumer.
- The next treaty deals with the personality of the brand as a reflective symbol of the consumer's self. Trademarks are often used by consumers as a means of expressing their identity. This identity can be either their true identity or a preferred or ideal self that they desire. Consumer personalities can express themselves through consumption and choice of specific brands. Consumers often make purchases for products that can make sense. The concept of a trademark can be an important factor in making decisions from consumers and acquiring a symbolic meaning creates a connection with the consumer. Through this connection a symbolic meaning of the product develops with the consumer. In this way the brand satisfies the consumer's desire and creates an emotional value through the simulation. Emotional value can influence consumer behavior and, at the same time, symbolic meaning can serve as a means of social interaction and communication. Consumers want to express themselves and use brands as a form of communication to express themselves.
- The latter treaty deals with the personality of the brand as a means of creating a consumer-brand relationship. This mode of action implies that all consumers do not choose brands that have similar personalities. Consumers prefer brands with different and opposing identities. Brand personality provides depth and feelings in the relationship between the brand and the consumer. Different consumers may have different types of relationships with a trademark based on the consumer's perception of the brand.

Personality and Emotions in Consumers

In international literature, the importance of emotion and traits of personality in decision making has been studied. The research is about to fully understand how consumers' use emotional information to make effective decisions according to their traits of personality. A growing body of research continues to focus on the emotions present in consumption situations, however a better understanding of emotional processing abilities can have important effects on consumer performance outcomes. Consumer emotional intelligence is defined here as a person's ability to use emotional information to achieve a desired consumer outcome, comprised as a set of first order emotional abilities that allow individuals to recognize the meanings of emotional patterns that underlie consumer decision making and to reason and solve problems on the basis of them. A better understanding of emotional ability can have considerable value in extending knowledge of consumer behavior. For example, it can provide answers to questions such as; how does emotional processing influence purchase decisions; which decisions do high vs. low EI consumers more readily make; how might EI influence relationships between key consumer variables such as impulsivity and purchase intention? Additionally, with this knowledge of emotional ability, we may be able to identify those consumer's who make the highest (and lowest) quality consumer decisions. For instance, consumers with high levels of nutrition knowledge who lack the emotional ability to understand which emotions are important and how to manage those emotions toward unhealthy eating, are likely to make poor quality decisions. Understanding these emotional deficiencies can provide a means to subsequently improve the quality of consumption decisions.

As far as the repercussion of personality traits in consumer behavior, recent advances in personality psychology can help us predict consumer motivation. Traits are defined as enduring and stable patterns of behavior, attitudes, emotions, that vary between individuals. Traditionally, researchers were interested in understanding how individuals differ, and so they put a great deal of effort into discovering how to measure, map, and define personality traits. An effort was made through trait theory in order to define personality traits. Trait theory suggests that personality is made up of a set of quantitative measurable characteristics or units known as traits. Traits are pre-dispositional attribute and are relatively stable. Every personality has a unique combination of traits and given its stability, people with a given combination of traits can be expected to behave consistently across situations and over time. Researchers are now reconceptualizing what traits are and where they come from--with traits being understood as chronic motivators that drive their decision-making. For example, researchers have linked personality traits to diverse outcomes such as experiential buying tendencies, political orientation, natural language use, preference in pets, the state of one's personal living space, and even more important life outcomes such as divorce, morbidity, and occupational attainment. Some recent data suggests that people who find themselves in disease-ridden environments tend to be less open and extraverted, presumably because this makes them less motivated to explore and interact with others (which reduces the chance they will become infected).

2.2. Data Mining Techniques

Data Mining is an emerging knowledge discovery process of extracting previously unknown, actionable information from very large scientific and commercial databases. It is imposed by the explosive growth of such databases. Usually, a data mining process extracts rules by processing high dimensional categorical and/or numerical data. Classification, clustering and association are the most well known data mining tasks. Classification is one of the most popular data mining tasks. Classification aims at extracting knowledge which can be used to classify data into predefined classes, described by a set of attributes. The extracted knowledge can be represented using various schemas. Decision trees, "if-then" rules and neural networks are the most popular such schemas. A lot of algorithms have been proposed in the literature for extracting classification rules from large relational databases, such as symbolic learning algorithms including decision trees algorithms (e.g. C4.5) and rule based algorithms (e.g. CN2), connectionist learning algorithms (e.g. back{propagation networks), instance-based algorithms (e.g. PEBLS) and hybrid algorithms. Association rules can be used to represent frequent patterns in data, in the form of dependencies among concepts attributes. In this paper, we consider the special case, that is known as the market basket problem, where concepts-attributes represent products and the initial database is a set of customer purchases (transactions).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Mining Association Rules

Association Rule Mining is a common technique used to find associations between many variables. In Data Mining, Apriori is a classic algorithm for learning association rules. Apriori is designed to operate on databases containing transactions (for example data collected from surveys in this case). As is common in

association rule mining, given a set of item sets, the algorithm attempts to find subsets which are common to at least a minimum number C of the itemsets.

Apriori uses a "bottom up" approach, where frequent subsets are extended one item at a time, and groups of candidates are tested against the data. The algorithm terminates when no further successful extensions are found. Apriori uses breadth-first search and a tree structure to count candidate item sets efficiently. It generates candidate item sets of length k from item sets of length k - 1. Then it prunes the candidates which have an infrequent sub pattern. According to the downward closure lemma, the candidate set contains all frequent k-length item sets. After that, it scans the transaction database to determine frequent item sets among the candidates.

Association rules present association or correlation between item sets. An association rule has the form of $A \rightarrow B$, where A and B are two disjoint item sets.

The Goal: studies whether the occurrence of one feature is related to the occurrence of others.

Three most widely used measures for selecting interesting rules are:

- ✓ **Support** is the percentage of cases in the data that contains both A and B,
- ✓ **Confidence** is the percentage of cases containing A that also contain B, and
- ✓ **Lift** is the ratio of confidence to the percentage of cases containing B.

3.2. Apriori rules visualization

Figure 1

- **Graph**
Represents the rules (or itemsets) as a graph. Specifically of our use, the parameters that were altered are:

`control=list(type="items")`

- **Grouped Matrix plot**

Antecedents (columns) in the matrix are grouped using clustering. Groups are represented as balloons in the matrix.

Figure 2

- **Paracord**

Parallel coordinate charts are a visualization that consists of N amount of vertical axes, each representing a unique data set of 61 rules, with lines drawn across the axes. The lines show the relationship between the axes, much like scatter plots, and the patterns that

Figure 3

the lines form indicates the relationship. We can also gather details about the relationships between the axes when you see the clustering of lines. Let's take a look at this using the chart below as an example. Specifically of our use, the parameters that were altered are:

➤ control=list(reorder=TRUE)

Apriori rules

For the top 24 rules that were extracted from the apriori the following parameters were altered:

- support: A numeric value for the minimal support of an item set
- confidence: A numeric value for the minimal confidence of rules/association hyperedges

Specifically of our use: Support: 0.6, Confidence: 0.9

After the extraction, the top 10 rules, also, presented lift approximately 1.

id	lhs	rhs	support	confidence	lift
414	{Do.you.think.it.is.necessary.for.your.purchases.to.be.followed.by.a.fashion.to.be.socially.acceptable=No, EPQ_L_Lie.Social.Desirability=HIGH}	=> {Prefer.your.purchases.to.be.made.from.only.one.particular.company=No}	0.5555556	0.9090909	1.105651
300	{Prefer.your.purchases.to.be.made.from.only.one.particular.company=No, BPA_Intimacy=LOW}	=> {BPA_Commitment=LOW}	0.4888889	0.9166667	1.269231
301	{BPA_Self.connection=LOW, BPA_Brand.personality.appeal=LOW}	=> {BPA_Attitudes.toward.public.relations=LOW}	0.4111111	0.9024390	1.269055
302	{BPA_Interdependence=LOW, BPA_Brand.personality.appeal=LOW}	=> {BPA_Attitudes.toward.public.relations=LOW}	0.4111111	0.9024390	1.269055
303	{BPA_Intimacy=LOW}	=> {BPA_Commitment=LOW}	0.6000000	0.9152542	1.267275
304	{BPA_Interdependence=LOW, BPA_Attitudes.toward.public.relations=LOW}	=> {BPA_Commitment=LOW}	0.4444444	0.9090909	1.258741
305	{EI_self_control=HIGH, EI_sociability=HIGH}	=> {EI_well_being=HIGH}	0.4333333	0.9069767	1.255814
306	{BPA_Self.connection=LOW, BPA_WOM.transmission=LOW}	=> {BPA_Commitment=LOW}	0.4333333	0.9069767	1.255814
307	{Prefer.your.purchases.to.be.made.from.only.one.particular.company=No, BPA_Self.connection=LOW}	=> {BPA_Commitment=LOW}	0.4111111	1.0000000	1.250000
309	{BPA_Interdependence=LOW, BPA_Attitudes.toward.advertising=LOW}	=> {BPA_Commitment=LOW}	0.4111111	0.9024390	1.249531

3.3. CorrelationAnalysis

Correlation is any of a broad class of statistical relationships involving dependence, though in common usage it most often refers to the extent to which two variables have a linear relationship with each other. Formally, random variables are dependent if they do not satisfy a mathematical property of probabilistic independence. In informal parlance, correlation is synonymous with dependence. However, when used in a technical sense, correlation refers to any of several specific types of relationship between mean values. There are several correlation coefficients, often denoted ρ or r , measuring the degree of correlation.

Correlation Matrix

Figure 4

The correlation matrix of n random variables X_1, \dots, X_n is the $n \times n$ matrix whose i, j entry is $\text{corr}(X_i, X_j)$. If the measures of correlation used are product-moment coefficients, the correlation matrix is the same as the covariance matrix of the standardized random variables $X_i / \sigma(X_i)$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$.

	BPA_Inter	BPA_Passi	BPA_Self.	BPA_Com	BPA_Intim	BPA_Trust	BPA_WON	BPA_Bran	BPA_Attit	BPA_Attit	EPQ_P_Ps	EPQ_N_N	EPQ_E_Ex	EPQ_L_Lie	EI_well_b	EI_self_co	EI_emotic	EI_sociabi
BPA_Inter	1	0.652026	0.563534	0.499829	0.52787	0.481945	0.367815	0.314412	0.268159	0.179651	-0.116	-0.15193	-0.02537	-0.1365	0.400338	0.306305	0.36266	0.299822
BPA_Passi	0.652026	1	0.66265	0.541944	0.558414	0.448366	0.475589	0.42894	0.3335	0.268616	0.006267	-0.07185	0.11847	-0.07028	0.34199	0.443831	0.375865	0.353172
BPA_Self.	0.563534	0.66265	1	0.609976	0.70519	0.61789	0.482206	0.519982	0.402041	0.405418	-0.03007	-0.03975	-0.04306	-0.0794	0.432358	0.266746	0.257627	0.314426
BPA_Com	0.499829	0.541944	0.609976	1	0.739097	0.633417	0.482815	0.447477	0.357187	0.487956	-0.09641	-0.15167	0.039218	-0.04322	0.273357	0.315429	0.274932	0.280788
BPA_Intim	0.52787	0.558414	0.70519	0.739097	1	0.853761	0.693173	0.708929	0.593741	0.443027	-0.00844	0.003631	0.002886	0.01345	0.349712	0.332152	0.312669	0.327018
BPA_Trust	0.481945	0.448366	0.61789	0.633417	0.853761	1	0.653856	0.712324	0.572445	0.573815	-0.04914	-0.01356	-0.06795	-0.01797	0.366622	0.312678	0.292638	0.409937
BPA_WON	0.367815	0.475589	0.482206	0.482815	0.693173	0.653856	1	0.768006	0.762599	0.573434	-0.05771	-0.03344	-0.05069	-0.12264	0.2836	0.397334	0.311891	0.371669
BPA_Bran	0.314412	0.42894	0.519982	0.447477	0.708929	0.712324	0.768006	1	0.635229	0.524368	-0.0273	-0.00622	0.001019	-0.06629	0.366461	0.439898	0.297171	0.39004
BPA_Attit	0.268159	0.3335	0.402041	0.357187	0.593741	0.572445	0.762599	0.635229	1	0.554699	-0.08582	-0.06553	-0.06516	-0.08143	0.243525	0.267179	0.179847	0.273882
BPA_Attit	0.179651	0.268616	0.405418	0.487956	0.443027	0.573815	0.573434	0.524368	0.554699	1	0.053564	-0.0459	-0.10163	-0.04097	0.352334	0.349515	0.28323	0.453325
EPQ_P_Ps	-0.116	0.006267	-0.03007	-0.09641	-0.00844	-0.04914	-0.05771	-0.0273	-0.08582	0.053564	1	0.600729	0.423031	0.57193	-0.09177	-0.31112	-0.30941	-0.17528
EPQ_N_N	-0.15193	-0.07185	-0.03975	-0.15167	0.003631	-0.01356	-0.03344	-0.00622	-0.06553	-0.0459	0.600729	1	0.132054	0.38591	-0.03268	-0.29821	-0.32105	-0.06252
EPQ_E_Ex	-0.02537	0.11847	-0.04306	0.039218	0.002886	-0.06795	-0.05069	0.001019	-0.06516	-0.10163	0.423031	0.132054	1	0.372321	-0.10449	-0.08629	-0.08691	-0.20771
EPQ_L_Lie	-0.1365	-0.07028	-0.0794	-0.04322	0.01345	-0.01797	-0.12264	-0.06629	-0.08143	-0.04097	0.57193	0.38591	0.372321	1	-0.15915	-0.31109	-0.26515	-0.15131
EI_well_b	0.400338	0.34199	0.432358	0.273357	0.349712	0.366622	0.2836	0.366461	0.243525	0.352334	-0.09177	-0.03268	-0.10449	-0.15915	1	0.562934	0.493751	0.696015
EI_self_co	0.306305	0.443831	0.266746	0.315429	0.332152	0.312678	0.397334	0.439898	0.267179	0.349515	-0.31112	-0.29821	-0.08629	-0.31109	0.562934	1	0.704924	0.628284
EI_emotic	0.36266	0.375865	0.257627	0.274932	0.312669	0.292638	0.311891	0.297171	0.179847	0.28323	-0.30941	-0.32105	-0.08691	-0.26515	0.493751	0.704924	1	0.644349
EI_sociabi	0.299822	0.353172	0.314426	0.280788	0.327018	0.409937	0.371669	0.39004	0.273882	0.453325	-0.17528	-0.06252	-0.20771	-0.15131	0.696015	0.628284	0.644349	1

Table 1

4. CONCLUSION

This study substantiates an important role in linking the personality of the brand name to the personality and emotional intelligence of the consumer. In this way, as found in this study, marketers have to step up their efforts to make brand personality more appealing to their target consumers. This study has some limitations such as the fact that it was tested with consumers from Greece in times of economic crisis. It is also necessary to test consumers from other markets in order to improve the generalization of the results of this research. Additional components of the marketing mix, such as pricing, promotion and product quality, can be added as part of the brand's personality. These are also directions for future research.

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